

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Volume 4; Issue 1; 2026; Page No. 09-24

Received: 11-10-2025

Accepted: 23-11-2025

Published: 10-01-2026

Investigating the Impact of Organizational Culture on Teacher Job Satisfaction in Private Christian Bible Schools in North Yangon

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18206952>

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon, Myanmar. This study employed four cultural dimensions (involvement, consistency, adaptability, and Mission) for a framework to understand how these traits influence teacher job satisfaction in these schools. The data is gathered from teachers in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon using a structured questionnaire on a Five-Point Likert scale. The results show that involvement has the most significant impact on teacher job satisfaction. Among these four dimensions, involvement ($p = 0.000$) and mission ($p = 0.008$) are the most influential elements based on regression coefficients. There are more male respondents (66.7%) who hold master's degrees (60.7%) and have extensive teaching experience. To further improve teacher job satisfaction, it is essential to pay attention to adaptability and consistency. The findings provide practical advice to school leaders to enhance teacher satisfaction and retention, which directly affects student learning outcomes and the long-term sustainability of private Christian Bible schools. This study helps fill the gap in understanding the role of organizational culture in private Christian Bible schools, laying the groundwork for further research and policy development.

Keywords: Investigating, Organizational Culture, North Yangon, Christian Bible, framework

1. Introduction

The success of a school largely depends on teachers' job satisfaction because most of the school's vital performance lies with teachers. Employees are the key players in the organization and are one of the most important determining factors and driving forces behind organizational success and competitiveness because of their involvement and commitment. Research confirmed that many satisfied employees contribute to organizational effectiveness (Mali *et al.*, 2022) [40]. If employees are satisfied with their jobs, it will enhance their performance, and the organization will fulfill its goals and objectives. That means job satisfaction is crucial for the success of an organization and influences its overall operations and goal achievement. It attracts good customers, maintains loyalty, and contributes to growth (Sahoo, 2020; Hosseinkhazadeh, Hosseinkhazadeh and

Yeganeh, 2013) [55, 26].

Organizational culture is a crucial factor in enhancing organizational output and productivity. Moynihan and Pandey's (2007) [46] study highlighted the significant impact of organizational culture on employee job satisfaction. Organizational culture is vital in influencing job satisfaction, as it significantly shapes the work environment and overall job satisfaction across various sectors. Significant researchers equate job satisfaction with organizational culture (Raj'ati and Jazaeri, 2016; Ahmed, 2017; Janićijević, Nikčević and Vasić, 2018; Nigatu, 2018; Par, 2019; Reidhead, 2020; Hagos, 2021; Mali *et al.*, 2022) [53, 3, 30, 48, 50, 54, 24, 40].

Job satisfaction among teachers is essential for service provider institutions like private Christian Bible schools because of their well-being, performance, retention, and

overall effectiveness of the schools. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction and its contribution to schools' competitive advantage. Recent studies have aimed at primary and secondary teachers (Muhammad Arifin, 2015; Mahar *et al.*, 2018; Fatima Kashif, Shaheen and Mannan, 2021; Mohamed, 2022; Alcantaradas, Leni and Francisco, 2024) [47, 38, 18, 45, 4]. Furthermore, previous literature provides limited evidence about religious institutions, with most studies focusing on state-owned higher educational institutions (Abumandil, 2012; Batugal and Tindowen, 2019; Serinkan and Kiziloglu, 2021; Mahindru and Kapoor, 2022) [1, 10, 58, 39]. Understanding and measuring the impacts of organizational culture on job satisfaction is essential for school leadership to achieve their goals. This research investigates organizational culture's impacts on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon.

1.1 History of Christian Bible Schools

The history of Christian Bible schools in Myanmar is related to the development of Christianity in Myanmar. According to research, there has been a Christian community in Myanmar since the beginning of the 16th century (Kham, 2015) [34]. With the rise of Philip Debrito in Syriam in 1600, the Portuguese brought Roman Catholicism to Myanmar (Shwe, 2020) [59]. The English Baptist missionaries Richard Marden and James Charter established the Protestant Mission in 1807 from Bengal in India (Lim and Dengthuama, 2016) [37]. Anglican, Roman Catholic, and American Baptist missionaries arrived in Myanmar and started the Western educational system by founding their churches and schools (Nwe, 2018) [49].

Christian churches in Myanmar have expanded their ministries, with Bible schools playing a crucial role in disciple-making. These schools impart sound theological principles to Christians, developing them into mature followers of Jesus Christ. Before 1980, no private Christian Bible schools existed in Myanmar, but Baptist and Anglican churches established their theological institutions. Many Christian leaders went abroad for further studies and returned to Myanmar to establish Bible schools.

1.1.1 Ownership of Christian Bible Schools

There are generally four types of Christian Bible school ownership: government ownership, non-denominational group ownership, denominational church ownership, and founder ownership. Public colleges or universities typically run under government ownership. Non-denominational group ownership involves individuals establishing regulations, budgets, and salaries. The church denomination owns denominational church ownership, while a person establishes founder ownership. Private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon fall under the fourth ownership category.

1.1.2 Schools' Calendar

Summer in Myanmar and private Christian Bible schools span February. Academic years usually start in June and end in February, divided into two semesters.

1.1.3 Schools' Curriculums and Library

Christian Bible schools provide a structured, systematically structured environment for students to study the Bible for three to four years under the guidance of qualified teachers. The curriculum includes Bible-related subjects like biblical theology, systematic theology, church history, English, psychology, and non-Christian religions. The schools also have a library of books, periodicals, and pamphlets to aid in exegetical and expository work in Scripture.

1.1.4 Mission and Vision Statement

Christian Bible schools are established to produce the next generation of well-rounded servant leaders for God and the community. These schools are committed to offering a thorough and balanced education and biblical training, promoting students' unique talents and understanding of Myanmar's culture. By attending Bible schools, students can apply what they learn in the classroom to outside events in society, be successful lifelong learners, and well-informed domestic and good global citizens. They learn to value diversity and are prepared for God's service in Myanmar.

1.1.5 Schools' Structure

Private Bible schools have qualified faculty and staff with undergraduate or graduate degrees. The school founder usually is the president, and the Academic Dean manages academic programs and activities. The Registrar keeps student admission and grade records. The dean of students supervises students' daily affairs and activities. A librarian is necessary for these schools because libraries are crucial for academic life. Schools strive to uphold high academic and spiritual standards. With strong theological credentials, each teacher is fully dedicated to Christ and the Bible to provide instruction in a style that both informs and edifies.

1.2 Justification and Significance of the Research

Many researchers affirmed that organizational culture significantly impacts employee job satisfaction (Gilbert, 1991; Fatima, 2016; Gligorović *et al.*, 2016; Ahmed, 2017; Sahoo, 2020; Hagos, 2021) [20, 19, 21, 3, 55, 24]. It is true in educational settings as well. It is well-known that satisfied teachers are more motivated, committed, and productive, enhance student outcomes, and fulfill the school's mission. However, there is a noticeable gap in research concentrating on religious educational institutions, particularly in Myanmar. There is a lack of information about how organizational culture impacts job satisfaction in religious institutions like private Christian Bible schools, as previous research has been done on secular educational institutions. Therefore, investigating the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon is relevant and necessary.

The findings of this research will be primarily valuable to leaders of private Christian Bible schools, helping them to realize how their organizational culture affects teacher job satisfaction. The findings will inspire them to address their weaknesses and strengths, leading to efficient and effective operations. The schools might also use the findings as input

to amend their policies and procedures on organizational culture and other human capital management strategies to enhance teacher satisfaction and retention, thereby improving overall school performance and student outcomes. Furthermore, the research will contribute to the existing knowledge base and serve as a benchmark for future research and as secondary data sources for similar studies.

1.3 Scope of the Research

The study was conducted in private Christian Bible Schools in North Yangon, focusing on four townships. Schools that have similar characteristics were chosen. Twenty private Christian Bible schools share identical characteristics in North Yangon, Myanmar. It was determined using simple random sampling techniques. Fifty percent of schools will be selected randomly for data collection.

Indeed, organizational cultural dimensions like power distance, uncertainty avoidance, gender, and individualism versus collectivism affect employee job satisfaction. Moreover, this study will concentrate solely on the four traits of organizational culture: involvement, consistency, adaptability, mission, and their impacts on teacher job satisfaction.

The proposed study involved teachers with varying levels of experience and from different departments within private Christian Bible Schools in North Yangon. However, administrative staff and students were excluded from data collection.

1.4 Research Methodology

This study employed a quantitative research design with a descriptive type to investigate the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible Schools in North Yangon. The target population includes teachers from ten schools, with cluster sampling methods used. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires using a Five-Point Likert scale to measure organizational culture and teacher job satisfaction. The Denison organizational culture survey was utilized for questionnaires of independent variables (involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission), and the Minnesota satisfaction questionnaire (short-form) for the dependent variable (teacher job satisfaction). Secondary data from relevant books, articles, journals, and internet websites were collected. Statistical Packages of Social Science (SPSS) was used for data analysis. Multiple regression analysis was applied to determine the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to derive meaningful insights and measure the mean value for each level of respondents.

2. Research Problem Identification and Statement

There is a unique culture in each organization with different features. Organizational culture refers to established beliefs, shared values, and norms that distinguish an organization and shape its workers' behavior and attitudes (Usman, 2019) [66]. The essential function of organizational culture is to establish the practices to be followed and to shape employee behavior within the organization. The culture within an organization is crucial because it influences the work environment for employee job satisfaction. Good interaction

between the culture and employees enhances job satisfaction, which fosters accomplishing the mission and objectives of the organization (Tedla, 2016) [63]. Since organizational culture advances employee commitment, motivation, morale, and job satisfaction, it is essential for the human resources management of any organization. However, dysfunction can be challenging as it affects effectiveness and job satisfaction without proper management (Nigatu, 2018) [48].

Private Christian Bible schools, as exceptional organizations, have their own unique organizational culture. A strong school culture contributes to the continued improvement and innovation of the educational system. Furthermore, it leads to realizing resources in and around the schools and ensures the quality of the learning experience (Turan Kurşun and Yılmaz, 2020) [65]. Therefore, it is crucial to identify and carefully manage organizational culture to ensure teacher job satisfaction so that the schools can fulfill their goals and objectives through satisfied teachers (Nigatu, 2018) [48].

When the values and norms align with employees' needs, organizational culture significantly impacts job satisfaction because it creates a model for everyday behavior and ensures a satisfying work environment where employees meet their needs (Qazi and Kaur, 2017) [51]. According to different literature, such as Nigatu (2018) [48], Tesfatsion (2011) [64], and Abumandil (2012) [1], various indicators are used to measure employee job satisfaction regarding organizational culture. Some significant factors include involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission. Not only has the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools not been investigated, but this topic has not been investigated from the lens of the above dimensions.

Good organizational culture leads to job satisfaction, which leads to job performance. Job satisfaction is crucial for ensuring sustainable growth and long-term profit and promoting a competitive advantage for any organization. Organizational culture is critical for job satisfaction (Par, 2019) [50]. According to Tesfatsion (2011) [64], researchers have no agreement about the relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction. However, there are multiple evidence given that support the correlation between organizational culture and job satisfaction (Davoodalmousavi, 2013; Gligorović *et al.*, 2016; Khadar, 2018; Ispik *et al.*, 2021; Jigjiddorj *et al.*, 2021; Hue *et al.*, 2022; Deepak Agarwal, 2023) [13, 21, 33, 32, 27, 29].

One of the most critical challenges for organizations, including private Christian Bible schools, is to develop and retain reliable and productive employees (Raj'ati *et al.*, 2016) [53]. It is undeniable in service-provided organizations, like education institutions, where teacher performance and satisfaction are essential to an organization's success. Teachers are the main backbone of educational institutions' success. Teacher job satisfaction is directly related to the quality of education they address. The importance of teacher job satisfaction regarding organizational culture is well-known, but its relationship is not investigated in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon.

Organizational culture significantly impacts teacher performance in educational settings, like job satisfaction, motivation, and commitment. Previous studies repeatedly

confirm that organizational culture influences teacher job satisfaction in educational contexts (Bashayreh, Assaf and Qudah, 2016; Jie *et al.*, 2017; Fatima Kashif, Shaheen and Mannan, 2021; Singh, 2021; Mahindru and Kapoor, 2022b; Mohamed, 2022) [9, 31, 18, 60, 39, 45]. Much investigation has been done concerning the relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction in various organizations (Ahamed and Mahmood, 2015; Imran and Binti Ismail, 2018; Das and Tripathy, 2020; Kumari and Mukherjee, 2021; Mali *et al.*, 2022) [2, 28, 12, 35, 40]. Still, the exclusive features of faith-based institutions like Christian Bible schools are regularly unobserved under distinct cultural and religious settings. So, there is a lack of literature that primarily deals with the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction in faith-based educational institutions, particularly private Christian Bible schools.

Few existing studies mainly focus on state-owned higher educational institutions, primary schools, and secondary schools (Miharty, 2013; Sangadji and Sopiah, 2013; Muhammad Arifin, 2015; Mahar *et al.*, 2018; Mishra and Vaidya, 2018; Serinkan and Kiziloglu, 2021; Mohamed, 2022) [43, 56, 47, 38, 44, 58, 45], causing a significant gap in understanding religious institutions like Christian Bible schools in Myanmar. The lack of study on this issue is problematic because private Christian Bible schools are vital in developing religious and ethical education for future generations. Furthermore, the lack of empirical research on the organizational culture of these schools explicitly demonstrates the need for more research on their challenges and opportunities.

The mission and beliefs of private Christian Bible schools shape their organizational culture, which, in turn, distinctly influences teacher job satisfaction. However, this has not been thoroughly examined. Filling this research gap is necessary for school leaders to make informed decisions, enhance teacher satisfaction and retention, and increase the quality of education. Eventually, this will help them achieve their school goals and objectives effectively.

The lack of school leaders' understanding of how organizational culture impacts teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools has severe implications for these institutions. Without a clear comprehension of the effect of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction, school leaders will face difficulty improving teacher morale, lowering turnover, and enhancing school performance. Ultimately, these schools will not be able to carry out their goals of providing the best quality of education and molding their students for the betterment of the world. Without job satisfaction, teacher turnover rates will increase, causing a drop in morale and eventually, a decline in the quality of education delivered.

No previous study has been conducted regarding the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction at private Christian Bible schools in north Yangon, Myanmar, which is why the researcher was passionate about pursuing this study. Therefore, the study seeks to fill this gap by addressing the following fundamental research questions:

- Which organizational culture traits significantly impact teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in north Yangon?
- What is the relationship between organizational culture

and teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in north Yangon?

- How do organizational culture traits (involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission) influence teacher job satisfaction?

2.1 Aims and Objectives of the Research

The primary aim of this study is to investigate organizational culture's impact on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon.

2.1.1 Objectives of the Research

- To identify the specific elements of organizational culture that most significantly influence teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon.
- To examine the relationship between organizational culture and teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon.
- To analyze the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon.

3. Selection and Application of Appropriate Techniques, Theories, Tools, and Practices

3.1 Introduction to Organizational Culture

Organizational culture plays a vital role in building unity and promoting continuous improvement. Effective culture leads organizations to tremendous success and is essential for preserving market position. It significantly impacts employee performance, productivity, commitment, retention, working relationships, procedures, and employee-employer interactions (Gull and Azam, 2012) [23].

The key feature that distinguishes successful organizations from others is organizational culture. Significant research has been done on organizational culture since the 1980s, with its important influence on performance and employee-related aspects. However, managing these cultures can be challenging for organizations' leaders as it is associated with an organization's uniqueness, values, mission, aims, goals, and shared beliefs. Thus, understanding and addressing organizational culture is critical for its significant impacts. Ignoring it can negatively affect organizational changes (Cameron and Quinn, 2006; Abumandil, 2012) [11, 1].

3.1.1 Definition and Importance of Organizational Culture

No definition accurately defines organizational culture, as it is a complex concept encompassing values, beliefs, and assumptions held by organizations' members. As the organization's bedrock, organizational culture influences the internal environment and employees' behavior. Many authors have differently defined in various sectors, including anthropology, psychology, and sociology. Most researchers agree that organizational culture is a collection of shared values, norms, and beliefs that affect how individuals connect and handle their jobs in their organizations (Aldhuwaihi, 2013) [5]. In this regard, Schein's (2010, p.18) [57] definition is one of the most comprehensive, describing it as "a pattern of shared basic assumptions that the group learned as it solved its problems of external

adaptation and internal integration that has worked well enough to be considered valid and, therefore, to be taught to new members of the organization as the correct way to perceive, think, and feel in relation to those problems.” Organizational culture is essential in promoting students' academic and spiritual development in private Christian Bible schools. It also influences teachers' behavior and dramatically impacts their job satisfaction, directly affecting their effectiveness and the school's success (Denison, 1990) [16].

3.1.2 Overview of Major Models of Organizational Culture:

There are valuable models for discovering and assessing organizational culture. Schein's model is one of the most well-known models. It arranges culture into three levels: artifacts, espoused values, and basic underlying assumptions (Schein, 2010) [57]. Artifacts refer to the most visible components of culture, like the physical and social environments, which significantly influence workplace culture. For instance, it encompasses employee dress code, office furniture, behavior, mission, and vision. Espoused values are employees stated principles and values, constituting organizational culture. It suggests that employee values influence organizational culture, and their thought processes and attitudes impact the workplace's culture. The third level includes employees' shared values, hidden beliefs, and inner aspects of human nature. Although Schein's model provides a thorough framework for understanding the complexity of organizational culture, its complexity makes it challenging to use in real-world research settings.

Cameron and Quinn (2006) [11] constructed a tool known as an Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI) to assess organizational culture. Hierarchy, market, clan, and adhocracy are the four organizational cultures of the Competing Values Framework (CVF), which is the foundation of OCAI. This model is valuable for evaluating how different cultural types correlate with employee satisfaction and organizational success. For instance, clan cultures improve employee morale and job satisfaction due to the strong emphasis on creating a family-like atmosphere. Market culture may not be relevant in an educational context as it concerns competitiveness and achieving measurable outcomes. Though CVF offers insight into how culture affects organizational outcomes, its primary concern is not the specific context of teacher job satisfaction but the overall organizational performance.

3.1.3 Denison's Cultural Model

As this research focuses on investigating the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools, Denison's cultural model is particularly well-suited for examining the specific cultural traits that impact job satisfaction. The model offers four key characteristics of organizational culture: involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission. The four traits are directly linked to organizational effectiveness and employee satisfaction (Denison, 1990) [16]. It focuses on the foundation of organizational culture, including assumptions and beliefs, and divides it horizontally and vertically. The following figure represents the organizational culture model.

Fig 1: Denison's model of organizational culture

- 1. Involvement:** It refers to employees' empowerment and participation in the organization's decision-making processes, which makes employees feel a strong sense of ownership. In other words, it emphasizes employees' involvement in the organization's aims, authority, collaboration, and capacity development. In private Christian Bible schools, teachers will feel a sense of ownership and commitment if involved in curriculum development, school administration, and school activities. When employees have high levels of involvement, they have increased job satisfaction because they feel more valued and empowered (Denison, 1990; 2006; Denison and Mishra, 1995) [16, 17].
- 2. Consistency:** Consistency and well-integration cause the success of organizations. These organizations have core values, skilled leaders, and well-coordinated and integrated activities. Consistent organizations create internal governance systems based on consensual support, using an implicit control system. Private Christian Bible schools' consistency is evident in their unified approach to teaching, discipline, and religious practices. Consistency in culture offers teachers a stable and predictable climate, increasing job satisfaction (Denison, 1990; 2006; Denison and Mishra, 1995) [16, 17].
- 3. Adaptability:** It describes an organization's ability to deal with external changes and challenges. Three indexes-creating change, customer focus, and organizational learning-measure this trait. It assesses an organization's ability to modify changing needs, expect future trends, and understand and satisfy customers while fostering innovation and knowledge acquisition. In private Christian Bible schools, adaptability refers to how the school successfully maintains its religious identity while responding to changes in educational standards, societal values, and the needs of the students. When schools are adaptable, they create a favorable environment where teachers feel adequately supported in leading changes, which can increase their overall job satisfaction (Denison, 1990; 2006; Denison and Mishra,

1995)^[16, 17].

4. **Mission:** It consists of an organization's goals, vision, and strategic objectives. The focus is on the clarity and communication of the organization's purpose and direction. When private Christian Bible schools have a clear and well-defined purpose based on Christian principles and educational goals, the teachers' personal beliefs will align with the schools' purpose. Schools with a strong and well-communicated mission give teachers a sense of purpose and meaning in their work, contributing to higher job satisfaction (Denison, 1990; 2006; Denison and Mishra, 1995)^[16, 17].

Denison's model is especially applicable to this research because it provides a precise and practical framework for comprehending how specific cultural traits impact teacher job satisfaction. As schools' success largely depends on the quality of teaching and teacher satisfaction, the model's emphasis on organizational effectiveness aligns with the educational setting.

3.1.4 Justification for Selecting Denison's Cultural Model

Though Schein's and the Competing Values Framework are valuable models for examining organizational culture, this study employs Denison's cultural model because of its practical applicability and relevance to research objectives. Denison's model connects specific cultural traits and organizational outcomes, such as employee satisfaction. This model is relevant for investigating how organizational culture relates to teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools.

Many studies in various sectors used Denison's model (Banto and Chandan, 2011; Allameh and Sarraf, 2013; Raj'ati *et al.*, 2016; Andrici, Amar and Masdupi, 2019; Par, 2019; Wahyuningsih *et al.*, 2019)^[8, 6, 53, 7, 50, 67]. Therefore, it is a reliable and established tool for cultural assessment. The four traits of this model – involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission - align well with religious schools' values and offer a comprehensive knowledge of how culture impacts teacher job satisfaction.

3.2 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction leads to organizational effectiveness. It also empowers employees to take charge and achieve organizational goals. Employees are vital for an organization's success, health, and sustainability. Organizational culture, performance, and job satisfaction are interrelated, and proper attention is needed to achieve goals efficiently. Higher job satisfaction leads to better productivity and organizational performance.

According to Aldhuwaihi (2013)^[5], organizational culture significantly influences key organizational variables and individual attitudes and behaviors, including job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is an essential feature of organizational behavior and influences the quality of the working environment within an organization.

Job satisfaction is a subjective concept, defined in various ways by many researchers based on their perspectives. Green (2000)^[22], stated that job satisfaction refers to positive emotions experienced when an individual's job meets or exceeds their expectations. Employees' unique

circumstances, such as needs, values, and expectations, influence this satisfaction. Job satisfaction can be defined as employees' positive and negative feelings about their jobs. According to Spector (2003) (cited in Aldhuwaihi, 2013)^[5], job satisfaction is "an attitudinal variable that reflects how people feel about their jobs overall as well as about various aspects of them." Job satisfaction is one of the key elements of an organization's success. The degree of employees' job satisfaction is critical to achieving goals and objectives as the organization continually endeavors to improve all aspects of its operations.

Job satisfaction is crucial for identifying employee performance, retention, and organizational effectiveness. In educational settings, job satisfaction defines teachers' well-being and the quality of education they deliver to their students. Therefore, investigating the factors that impact teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools is necessary for teacher retention and student success.

3.2.1 Job Satisfaction Theories

Specific key theories must be studied in investigating the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools. They are necessary for finding different aspects that impact job satisfaction and the cultural traits of organizations that influence it. According to Green (2000)^[22], the theories are categorized into three: content, process, and situational theories. They provide a framework for understanding the psychological significance of job satisfaction.

3.2.1.1 Content theories

According to these theories, job satisfaction occurs when a worker's need for growth and self-actualization is met. Content theories seek to understand what people want to satisfy and the factors influencing their behavior by focusing on needs and values that motivate individuals and enhance their satisfaction and performance (Malo, 2015; Nigatu, 2018, Tesfatsion, 2011; Aldhuwaihi, 2013)^[64, 48, 5]. The following are summaries of two of the many content theories.

(a) Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory

It is one of the most used theoretical frameworks in studies on job satisfaction. According to this theory, two distinct factors-motivators and hygiene in the workplace-influence job satisfaction and dissatisfaction. It claims that motivators cause job satisfaction, and that lack of hygiene causes job dissatisfaction (Herzberg, Mausner and Snyderman, 1959)^[25].

Motivators: Intrinsic factors, like achievement, recognition, work itself, responsibility, advancement, and growth opportunities, promote job satisfaction.

Hygiene Factors: These are extrinsic factors, like relationships, work conditions, status, salary, and job security, which do not necessarily enhance job satisfaction but may cause dissatisfaction if insufficient.

Herzberg's theory is relevant because it clarifies how certain aspects of the organizational culture in private Christian Bible schools impact teachers' satisfaction and dissatisfaction. It is imperative to prioritize motivators and

hygiene factors in a culture to enhance teacher job satisfaction.

(b) Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Maslow's hierarchy of needs classified different human needs into physiological, safety, love, esteem, and self-actualization. It offers a complete framework for understanding job satisfaction (Maslow, 1943) [42]. According to Maslow (1943) [42], human needs are arranged in a hierarchy, from basic physiological needs to self-actualization, and fulfilling human needs is necessary for both physical and psychological health, affecting human behavior when satisfied. This theory argues that unmet needs serve as motivators, and once these needs are satisfied, individuals will move to satisfy higher needs in the hierarchy. In this way, job satisfaction is achieved when these needs are met, from the most fundamental to the most complex.

Maslow's theory is relevant to this research because it shows the importance of a supportive work environment in fulfilling teachers' various needs, from basic security to personal development. Meeting these needs through a strong organizational culture will increase teacher job satisfaction.

3.2.1.2 Process theories

These theories explain the energization, direction, maintenance, and stopping of a worker's behavior (Nigatu, 2018; Aldhuwaihi, 2013) [48, 5]. The following are summaries of two of the most well-known process theories.

- a. **Expectancy theory:** This theory argues that people are driven by their needs and choices regarding what they will do and not do and make decisions based on their perceived abilities to perform the work and get rewards. In decision-making, this theory uses three variables: expectancy, instrumentality, and valence. High positive values regarding these variables cause motivated performance, and the opposite is true. According to Green (2000) [22],
- b. **Equity theory:** This theory proposes that workers compare their outcome/input ratio to another person's outcome/input ratio, called a 'referent.' Equity occurs when an individual's outcome-to-input ratio equals another's outcome-to-input. Unequal ratios cause job dissatisfaction and motivate workers to restore equity (Green, 2000; Tesfatsion, 2011) [22, 64]. Outcomes refer to pay, fringe benefits, status, opportunities for advancement, job security, and anything of personal value that a worker gets from an organization. Inputs refer to special skills, training, education, work experience, effort on the job, time, and anything a worker thinks they contribute to an organization (Tsefatsion, 2011) [64].

3.2.1.3 Situational theory

This theory focuses on two elements: situational characteristics and situational occurrences. Situational characteristics such as pay, promotion opportunities, working conditions, policies, and supervision are evaluated before accepting a job, and situational occurrences are evaluated afterward. This theory suggests that overall satisfaction results from these two factors (Green, 2000; Tesfatsion, 2011) [22, 64].

3.2.3 Measurement of Job Satisfaction

It is not easy to measure job satisfaction as it is a subjective personal cognition in a person's mind. Just as there is no single definition of job satisfaction, there is no single way to measure it. The most used methods for indirectly measuring job satisfaction are observing employees, interviewing them, and asking them to complete questionnaires. Green (2000) [22] and Nigatu (2018) [48] suggested that measuring job satisfaction can be done by using either single-item, general, or facet measures such as The Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) (Spector, 1997) [62], The Job Descriptive Index (JDI) (Smith, Kendall and Hulin, 1969) [61], and The Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) (Weiss *et al.*, 1969) [68]. This research uses The Minnesota Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) short form, which includes 20 questions on intrinsic and extrinsic reinforcement factors of employee attitude.

3.3 The Relationship between Organizational Culture and Job Satisfaction

Organizational culture and job satisfaction are two intertwined aspects that significantly impact an individual's experience. Much research literature has examined the complex relationship between these two factors. The findings highlight the crucial roles of these two factors in organizational success and employee well-being (Yaswanth Kumar, 2023) [52].

Tsefatsion (2011) [64] examined the relationship between organizational culture and employee job satisfaction among academic staff in a private higher educational institution called St. Mary's University College using the OCAI and Minnesota Job Satisfaction Questionnaire. The findings showed that the most desired culture type was clan culture and hierarchy culture negatively affected overall teachers' job satisfaction. There was a positive and significant relationship between market culture and job satisfaction.

Malo's (2015) [41] research found a significant correlation between organizational culture and job satisfaction among academic professionals at the University of Technology in the Free State Province, South Africa. According to the research, the academic professionals had positive perceptions of the organizational culture within the institution, and they were satisfied with co-worker relations, supervision support, and the work itself.

Lang's (2011) [36] study proved that occupational stress and organizational culture significantly predict job satisfaction. According to Janićević, Nikčević and Vasić (2018) [30], various job satisfaction levels exist in different organizational culture types. Mohamed (2022) [45] researched the influence of school culture on teachers' job satisfaction at some selected secondary schools in Mogadishu, Somalia. He concluded his study by revealing that organizational culture, such as teamwork, reward, and training and development, positively affects teacher job satisfaction.

Private Christian Bible schools may effectively direct the intrinsic and extrinsic factors influencing job satisfaction by applying Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs to their organizational culture. If these schools develop an organizational culture that meets the basic needs of teachers and offers opportunities, it will significantly enhance teacher job satisfaction.

3.4 Previous Studies

Many studies have been conducted on the impact of organizational culture on job satisfaction, using different types of organizational culture as independent variables. However, only a few studies use Denison’s organizational culture traits to research the above. According to Raj’ati *et al.*, (2016) [53] study on “exploring the effect of organizational culture on job satisfaction: the case of Namvaran Consulting Engineers, Managers Company,” consistency was the most significant contributor to job satisfaction. It fulfilled the study’s aim of providing guidelines to HR managers.

Par (2019) [50] utilized Denison’s organizational culture traits to study the effect of organizational culture on job satisfaction and job performance of auditors at MAT professional firms in Myanmar. The findings efficiently showed that mission and consistency positively affected the job satisfaction of audit professionals.

By applying the Denison model, Banto and Chandan (2011) [8] investigated the effect of organizational culture traits on various aspects of organizational effectiveness, including employee satisfaction. The research found that the four organizational culture traits- involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission - all positively impacted firm effectiveness in 51 U.S. subsidiaries.

Using Denison’s organizational culture model, Allameh and Sarraf’s (2013) [6] study confirmed a correlation between organizational culture and job satisfaction and a significant effect on predicting job satisfaction. The findings of Wahyuningsih *et al.*, (2019) [67] show the importance of Denison’s organizational culture model in enhancing business competitiveness, especially hotel business by international management chain.

3.5 Conceptual Framework of the Research

This study creates a conceptual framework based on academic and literature reviews to conceptualize the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. This conceptual framework demonstrates how organizational culture impacts teacher job satisfaction. Two significant sections are involved in the conceptual framework of this study. Organizational culture (involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission) is an independent variable correlated to a dependent variable (teacher job satisfaction). The following figure depicts the conceptual framework of the study.

Fig 2: Source: Own compilation based on previous studies

4. Presentation of Analysis and Findings

4.1 Overview of Research Methodology and Data Collection:

This study employed a quantitative research

design with a descriptive type to investigate the impact of organizational culture on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible Schools in North Yangon. The target population includes teachers from ten schools, and cluster sampling methods were used. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires using a Five-Point Likert scale to measure organizational culture and teacher job satisfaction. Secondary data from relevant books, articles, journals, and internet websites were collected.

The study used both descriptive and inferential statistics. In descriptive statistics, terms such as frequency, table, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were applied. Inferential statistics was used to make inferences about a larger population. Reliability tests (Cronbach's alpha) and factor analysis were applied to test data reliability and validity. Correlation and multiple linear regression analyses were employed to determine the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Statistical Packages of Social Science (SPSS) was used for data analysis. A random sample of five schools was selected from among the ten clusters of schools. The selected cluster of five private schools is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Random Sample of Selected Schools

No.	Name	No. of Respondents
1.	School A	23
2.	School B	21
3.	School C	15
4.	School D	13
5.	School E	12
Total		84

Source: Survey Data (November 2024)

4.1.1 Reliability of Data

Reliability analysis focuses on the properties of measurement scales and the items that make up a scale and gives some basic indices for the scale’s reliability. It deals with reliability issues through reliability tests and calculates the internal consistency through Cronbach’s alpha tests. Cronbach’s alpha values are interpreted as follows: values below 0.6 are considered poor, values between 0.6 and 0.7 are questionable, 0.7 and 0.8 are acceptable, 0.8 and 0.9 are good, and 0.9 and above are excellent.

4.1.2 Validity of Data

Table 2: Reliability Analysis of Research Instrument

Variable	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Involvement	12	0.895
Consistency	12	0.941
Adaptability	12	0.936
Mission	12	0.944
Teacher Job Satisfaction	20	0.967

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

The table above displays the reliability coefficient for the research measures for the study; thus, Cronbach’s alpha coefficients for the research measures ranged from 0.895 to 0.967, hence showing the internal consistency of the measures. In detail, the reliability assessment presents Cronbach’s Alpha estimations of each variable: the involvement variable complies with 0.895, which is a highly

satisfactory level and implies that the items applied to solitary this construct are reliable. Details of the internal reliability analysis for the consistency variable yield an alpha of 0.941, which indicates excellent reliability. Likewise, the scores of adaptabilities represent this variable with a reliability coefficient of 0.936, which increases confidence in the validity of this scale as a measure of adaptability. For the mission variable, Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.944; this figure also suggests high reliability and supports the conclusion that the items measuring the mission aspect are also homogeneous. Finally, the self-developed measurement scale for teacher job satisfaction obtains a Cronbach alpha of 0.967, indicating the observed items’ internal reliability of the observed items. Thus, the findings of this analysis confirm the reliability and appropriateness of the used research instrument for further analysis in this study.

4.2 Demographic Profiles of Survey Respondents

The profiles of survey respondents were examined based on their gender, age, marital status, education level, and years of service. A total of 84 respondents have participated in this study.

4.2.1 Gender of Teachers

The gender of teachers is studied based on their sex: male and female. The study results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Gender of Teachers

No.	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Male	56	66.7
2.	Female	28	33.3
Total		84	100.0

Source: Survey Data (November 2024)

It was discovered that most teachers are male. The number of male respondents is 56, 66.7% of the sample population, while the remaining (33.3%) are female. Thus, there are more male than female teachers. According to the data, men dominate, with 66.7%, but teachers still have an equal chance of employment. The reason why there are more male teachers than female is because of the theology and principles of these institutions.

4.2.2 Age of Teachers

The age of teachers is studied by classifying five groups: 25 years and below, 26 – 30 years, 31 – 35 years, 36 – 40 years, and 41 years and above. The study results are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4: Age of Teachers

No.	Age Group (Year)	Frequency	Percentage
1.	25 and below	14	16.7
2.	26 - 30	9	10.7
3.	31 – 35	18	21.4
4.	36 - 40	17	20.2
5.	41 and above	26	31
Total		84	100.0

Source: Survey Data (November 2024)

Based on survey results, it is found that 16.7% of teachers are in the age group of 25 years and below. Moreover, 10.7% are between the ages of 26 and 30; 21.4% are between the ages of 31 and 35, 20.2% are between the ages of 36 and 40, and 31% are 41 years and above. As a result, most teachers are 36 or older. It is because, at this age, teachers have enough work experience, are capable of handling any orders from colleagues, and can solve any unexpected problems using their critical thinking.

4.2.3 Marital Status of Teachers

The marital status of teachers is studied by classifying them into two categories: married and single. The study results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Marital Status of Teachers

No.	Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Married	59	70.2
2.	Single	25	29.8
Total		84	100.0

Source: Survey Data (November 2024)

According to Table 5, it is found that 70.2% of teachers are married, compared to 29.8% who are single. Thus, most of them are married. This implies that the schools have steady teachers who can attend work while experiencing little frustration and who also have healthy families, which makes a significant contribution to the operation of the institutions.

4.2.4 Education Level of Teachers

Teachers’ education level is studied by five groups: diploma, bachelor, master, doctorate, and others. The study results are displayed in Table 6.

Table 6: Education Level of Teachers

No.	Education	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Diploma	2	2.4
1.	Bachelor	19	22.6
2.	Master	51	60.7
3.	Doctorate	10	11.9
4.	Others	2	2.4
Total		84	100.0

Source: Survey Data (November 2024)

According to Table 6, 2.4% of teachers have diplomas; 22.6% hold a bachelor’s degree; 60.7% hold master’s degrees; 11.9% hold doctorate degrees and 2.4% hold other certificates. Thus, most of them have master’s degrees. This means that the schools value the trained teachers’ contribution to their development, which will probably improve their efficiency.

4.2.5 Service Years of Teachers

The service years of teachers are studied by classifying five groups: below 1 year, 1 – 5 years, 6 – 10 years, 11 – 15 years, and 16 years and above. The study results are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Service Year of Teachers

No.	Service Year	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Less than one year	7	8.3
2.	1 – 5	30	35.7
3.	6 – 10	22	26.2
4.	11 – 15	8	9.5
5.	16 and above	16	20.2
Total		84	100.0

Source: Survey Data (November 2024)

According to Table 7, 8.3% of teachers have less than one year of service, 35.7% have one to five years, 26.2% have six to ten years, 9.5% have eleven to fifteen years, and 20.2% have sixteen years or more. Most of them have service years of more than six years and above. Thus, the schools have teachers with long service years rather than a new and fresh workforce.

4.3 Analysis and Findings

4.3.1 Descriptive Analysis of Teachers’ Perception of Involvement

The descriptive analysis of teachers’ perception of involvement was measured using 12 statements on a Likert scale of 5. In this scale, numbers correspond to 1=Very Dissatisfied, 2=Dissatisfied, 3=Neutral, 4=Satisfied, and 5=Very Satisfied. The mean values for each statement have been outlined in Table 8 below.

Table 8: Teachers’ Perception of Involvement

Sr. No.	Statements	Mean Value	Std. Deviation
1	Decisions are usually made at the level where the best information is available.	4.54	0.752
2	Information is widely shared so that everyone can get the information needed when it's needed.	4.58	0.662
3	Everyone believes that he or she can have a positive impact.	4.52	0.667
4	Business planning is ongoing and involves everyone in the process to some degree.	4.33	0.683
5	Cooperation across different parts of the organization is actively encouraged.	4.57	0.682
6	People work like they are part of a team.	4.38	0.79
7	Teamwork is used to get work done, rather than hierarchy.	4.38	0.638
8	Work is organized so that each person can see the relationship between their job and organizational goals.	4.48	0.57
9	Authority is delegated so that people can act on their own.	4.35	0.814
10	The "bench strength" (capability of people) is constantly improving.	4.26	0.661
11	There is continuous investment in the skills of employees.	4.38	0.849
12	The capabilities of people are viewed as an important source of competitive advantage.	4.31	0.821
Overall Mean		4.41	0.716

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

The above findings show that the level of agreement regarding the involvement of the teachers in organizational culture was at mean values of the statements that ranged from 4.26 to 4.58. The statement, which received the highest mean score of 4.58, indicates that the teachers are satisfied with the information-sharing level in their institution. Information is widely shared so everyone can get the needed information when needed. The statement ‘The "bench strength" (capability of people) is constantly improving’ received the lowest mean score of 4.26, which is still positive but may indicate that the involvement could be further improved as the capability enhances perception. The overall mean was 4.41, indicating that the teachers substantially agreed with the organizational activities, affirming the importance of participative decision-making, teamwork, and information sharing in enhancing satisfaction at the workplace.

4.3.2 Descriptive Analysis of Teachers’ Perception of Consistency

The descriptive analysis of teachers’ perception of consistency was measured using 12 statements on a Likert scale of 5. In this scale, numbers correspond to 1=Very Dissatisfied, 2=Dissatisfied, 3=Neutral, 4=Satisfied, and 5=Very Satisfied. The mean values for each statement have been outlined in Table 9 below.

Table 9: Teachers’ Perception of Consistency

Sr. No.	Statements	Mean Value	Std. Deviation
1	The leaders and managers "practice what they preach."	4.44	0.717
2	There is a clear and consistent set of values that governs the way we do business.	4.50	0.668
3	When people ignore our core values, they are held accountable.	4.30	0.889
4	There is an ethical code that guides our behavior and tells us right from wrong.	4.48	0.719
5	When disagreements occur, we work hard to achieve “win-win” solutions.	4.21	0.983
6	There is a clearly defined culture.	4.44	0.734
7	It is easy to reach a consensus, even on difficult issues.	4.38	0.835
8	There is a clear agreement about the right way and the wrong way to do things.	4.45	0.666
9	Our approach to doing business is very consistent and predictable.	4.39	0.792
10	People from different parts of the organization share a common perspective.	4.39	0.822
11	It is easy to coordinate projects across different parts of the organization.	4.30	0.889
12	There is good alignment of goals across levels.	4.45	0.666
Overall Mean		4.40	0.782

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

The mean scores for all the statements concerning consistency ranged from 4.21 to 4.50, thus showing a high level of satisfaction among the respondents. It means that teachers firmly believe that there are clear and well-

sustained principles of the organization’s functioning. Both statements concerning the agreement on goals and the right and wrong way to perform tasks received higher mean values of 4.45 each. The statement with the lowest mean score of 4.21 concerned attaining ‘win-win’ solutions in conflict situations, indicating some concerns related to conflict management practices. The results of the overall mean score of 4.40 also indicate that the teachers approve of the organizational culture as positive and suitable for organizational practice, thus positively impacting job satisfaction.

4.3.3 Descriptive Analysis of Teachers’ Perception of Adaptability

The descriptive analysis of teachers’ perception of adaptability was measured using 12 statements on a Likert scale of 5. In this scale, numbers correspond to 1=Very Dissatisfied, 2=Dissatisfied, 3=Neutral, 4=Satisfied, and 5=Very Satisfied. The mean values for each statement have been outlined in Table 10 below.

Table 10: Teachers’ Perception of Adaptability

Sr. No.	Statements	Mean Value	Std. Deviation
1	The way things are done is very flexible and easy to change.	4.45	0.937
2	We respond well to competitors and other changes in the business environment.	4.25	0.917
3	New and improved ways to do work are continually adopted.	4.44	0.75
4	Different parts of the organization often cooperate to create change.	4.42	0.748
5	Customer comments and recommendations often lead to changes.	4.38	0.805
6	Customer input directly influences our decisions.	4.21	1.087
7	All members have a deep understanding of customer wants and needs.	4.37	0.875
8	We encourage direct contact with customers by our people.	4.48	0.736
9	We view failure as an opportunity for learning and improvement.	4.58	0.605
10	Innovation and risk-taking are encouraged and rewarded.	4.33	0.812
11	Learning is an important objective in our day-to-day work.	4.68	0.541
12	We make certain that everyone is informed about what is going on across the organization.	4.48	0.752
Overall Mean		4.42	0.797

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

The results of the analysis of teachers’ perceptions of organizational adaptability are also encouraging, pointing towards high satisfaction levels concerning adaptability-related practice within organizations. The mean score of “Learning is an important objective in our day-to-day work” is 4.68, and teachers strongly concur with implementing learning. The lowest mean value is 4.21 for the statement “Customer input directly influences our decisions” “almost implying that this company is not as adaptive to customer needs as the other companies in the study but still has a

positive response. As a result, the overall mean of 4.42 indicates that most of the teachers are highly satisfied with the adaptability traits in their organizational culture. These efforts suggest how organizations foster learning, innovation, and organizational responsiveness to changes and customer feedback.

4.3.4 Descriptive Analysis of Teachers’ Perception of Mission

The descriptive analysis of teachers’ perception of mission was measured using 12 statements on a Likert scale of 5. In this scale, numbers correspond to 1=Very Dissatisfied, 2=Dissatisfied, 3=Neutral, 4=Satisfied, and 5=Very Satisfied. The mean values for each statement have been outlined in Table 11 below.

Table 11: Teachers’ Perception of Mission

Sr. No.	Statements	Mean Value	Std. Deviation
1	There is a long-term purpose and direction.	4.57	0.626
2	Our strategy leads other organizations to change the way they compete in the industry.	4.31	0.905
3	There is a clear mission that gives meaning and direction to our work.	4.55	0.701
4	There is a clear strategy for the future.	4.45	0.751
5	There is widespread agreement about goals.	4.54	0.735
6	Leaders set goals that are ambitious but realistic.	4.49	0.752
7	The leadership has clearly stated the objectives we are trying to meet.	4.51	0.72
8	We continuously track our progress against our stated goals.	4.27	0.923
9	We have a shared vision of what the organization will be like in the future.	4.40	0.808
10	Leaders have a long-term viewpoint.	4.40	0.793
11	Our vision creates excitement and motivation for our employees.	4.36	0.873
12	We are able to meet short-term demands without compromising our long-term vision.	4.39	0.776
		4.44	0.780

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

According to Table 12, The mean value is the highest at 4.57 on the statement “There is a long-term purpose and direction.” That means teachers strongly agree that the organization has a long-term focus. The statement with the lowest mean value, 4.27, is, “We continually monitor our progress on our stated objectives.” It suggests a more extensive area where organizations could improve how they systematically monitor their progress. The overall mean value can be seen to have a strong correlation and clarity with organizational mission, while leadership and goal setting are key determinants of teachers’ satisfaction. This sturdy perception accentuates the coherent and efficient dissemination and accomplishment of strategic initiatives in the organizational context.

4.3.5 Descriptive Analysis of Teachers’ Perception of Job Satisfaction

The descriptive analysis of teachers’ perception of job

satisfaction was measured using 20 statements on a Likert scale of 5. In this scale, numbers correspond to 1=Very Dissatisfied, 2=Dissatisfied, 3=Neutral, 4=Satisfied, and 5=Very Satisfied. The mean values for each statement have been outlined in Table 12 below.

Table 12: Teachers’ Perception of Job Satisfaction

Sr. No.	Statements	Mean Value	Std. Deviation
1	Being able to keep busy all the time	4.25	0.774
2	The chance to work alone on the job	4.25	0.790
3	The chance to do different things from time to time	4.32	0.779
4	The chance to be “somebody” in the community	4.35	0.720
5	The way my boss handles his/her workers	4.35	0.768
6	The competence of my supervisor in making decisions	4.35	0.857
7	Being able to do things that don’t go against my conscience	4.36	0.722
8	The way my job provides for steady employment	4.35	0.829
9	The chance to do things for other people	4.49	0.611
10	The chance to tell people what to do	4.48	0.736
11	The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities	4.37	0.741
12	The way company policies are put into practice	4.36	0.771
13	My pay and the amount of work I do	4.35	0.843
14	The chances for advancement on this job	4.35	0.857
15	The freedom to use my own judgment	4.32	0.809
16	The chance to try my own methods of doing the job	4.32	0.794
17	The working condition	4.37	0.757
18	The way my co-workers get along with each other	4.48	0.685
19	The praise I get for doing a good job	4.35	0.885
20	The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job	4.44	0.717
Overall Mean		4.37	0.772

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

The findings in this study are that the mean response for the statements is, on average, 4.25 to 4.49, which indicates a high level of teachers’ job satisfaction to the different dimensions of job satisfaction. The statement with the highest mean score of 4.49 for this study was “The opportunity to do things for other people, for example helping students. The lowest mean of 4.25, which means “Being able to keep busy all the time” and “The chance to work alone on the job” may not be important to the respondents. The overall mean of 4.37 suggests that Private Christian Bible Schools in North Yangon teachers are fairly satisfied. These facts can evidence the current policies and practices used in creating a positive work climate to promote job satisfaction and indicate areas that can be further improved to accommodate additional reforms to sustain the already set job satisfaction indicators.

4.4 Relationship between Organizational Culture and Teachers' Job Satisfaction

The correlation analysis was conducted to analyze the correlation between organizational culture dimensions and teachers’ job satisfaction in Private Christian Bible Schools in North Yangon the correlation analysis was conducted. Involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission of organizational culture dimension were used to test the relationship between organizational culture and teachers’ job satisfaction. The findings of this study are presented in the following table: Table 13.

Table 13: Correlation between Organizational Culture and Teachers' Job Satisfaction

No.	Description	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	P-Value
1	Involvement	.563**	.000
2	Consistency	.419**	.000
3	Adaptability	.397**	.000
4	Mission	.357**	.001

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

Based on the results presented in Table 14, it can be concluded that all the dimensions of organizational culture positively influence teachers’ job satisfaction. Involvement has the highest correlation coefficient, which is equal to .563. Therefore, increased involvement within the organization significantly improves teachers’ job satisfaction. This indicates that when teachers are included in the organizational and decision-making processes necessary in their workplaces, they are more satisfied with their roles.

The level of consistency is also directly related to job satisfaction, with a coefficient of .419. This shows that providing a good and coherent set of values and practices within the organization is necessary. Everyone will feel that the system is dependable, leading to increased teacher satisfaction levels. Likewise, adaptability is positively correlated with a value of .397, meaning the capability of the organization to manage change and foster the spirit of innovation improves the satisfaction levels of teachers. The mission dimension has a positive correlation coefficient of .357, indicating teachers’ job satisfaction. This implies that a focused, well-understood, and long-term organizational vision leads to substantive job satisfaction among the teachers.

The four theoretical organizational culture measures - involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission - are compared to teacher job satisfaction. Involvement seems to exert the most impact. It emphasizes the need to develop an effective climate to improve teachers’ job satisfaction in Private Christian Bible Schools in North Yangon.

4.5 Impact of Organizational Culture on Teachers' Job Satisfaction

4.5.1 Model Summary

The multiple linear regression analysis was run to analyze the effects of involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission organizational culture dimensions for teachers’ job satisfaction in Private Christian Bible Schools in North Yangon. The proposed model summary is provided in Table 14.

Table 14: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.678	.460	.432	.313

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

The overall value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.460. Thus, it indicates that 46.0% of teachers' job satisfaction variation has been predicted by the organizational culture factors incorporated in the anticipated model. It means that the four dimensions analyzed in the present study account for almost half of the total variation in job satisfaction, pointing toward the immense importance of these dimensions for the satisfaction experienced by teachers.

4.5.2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Table 15 presents the results of the regression model's overall test using the ANOVA test, where the 'Sig.' value represents the statistical significance of the model's fit.

Table 15: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	6.584	4	1.646	16.808	.000
Residual	7.737	79	.098		
Total	14.321	83			

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

The significance level of the regression model is determined by the p-value (Sig.) which is equal to .000. The F-statistic value of 16.808 indicates that involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission models, taken together, significantly predict a part of the variance in the level of job satisfaction among teachers. It implies that independent variables have the greatest effect on job satisfaction.

4.5.3 Regression Coefficients

The regression coefficients show the effects of the organizational culture dimensions, involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission on teacher job satisfaction.

Table 16: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	1.060	.359		.004
Involvement	.286	.068	.390	.000
Consistency	.160	.065	.218	.017
Adaptability	.121	.068	.166	.078
Mission	.171	.063	.231	.008

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

Table 16 shows the coefficients of determination for assessing the output of each dimension identified by employing linear regression. Of all the independent variables, involvement has a Beta coefficient of 0.390 and a p-value of 0.000, showing the highest positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at a 1% significance level, implying that a high level of involvement increases job satisfaction. The findings reveal that consistency predicts satisfaction at the 5% level (Beta = 0.218, p =

0.017), while mission is a statistically significant predictor at the 1% level (Beta = 0.231, p = 0.008). Finally, adaptability, which has a p-value of 0.078, is statistically significant at a 10% level. Therefore, it can be concluded that it positively affects teacher satisfaction to a lesser extent than the primary factors.

5. Presentation of Solutions and Recommendations

This section presents solutions, recommendations, findings, and discussions of the study's results. It also includes suggestions for further research.

5.1 Discussions of Findings

This study aims to analyze organizational culture attributes and their effects on teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon. The findings offer valuable information on the association between the various organizational culture traits, the independent variables, and teacher job satisfaction, the dependent variable. Based on the study's objectives, the results are analyzed and discussed.

The descriptive analysis suggests that teachers feel a high level of satisfaction for all the organizational culture dimensions, whereby the mean values obtained for the four dimensions were above 4.0 for mission, adaptability, consistency, and involvement, respectively. Mission receives the highest mean of 4.44, showing that teachers concurred with the organization's clear direction and vision in the school's mission statement. It emphasizes the necessity of a clear vision to motivate the teachers. Involvement is close to adaptation, with an average of 4.42, indicating teachers appreciate roles such as flexibility, creativity, and participation in organizational processes. The last important factor is consistency, which has a mean value of 4.39, reinforcing the vision that set values and practices are crucial to bring satisfaction.

Based on the results of the correlation analysis, the increase in the level of organizational culture is followed by a high teacher job satisfaction rate. Mission is positively correlated with job satisfaction, at the $r = .357, p < 0.01$, proving that a clear and inspiring goal statement makes a difference in workers' morale. The most substantial positive coefficient of correlation ($r = 0.563, p = 0.001$) illustrates the necessity of involvement, proving that the most active participation of teachers in decision-making and collaboration with others will satisfy them. Consistency ($r = .419, p < 0.01$) is also positively significant, highlighting that, for the teachers to trust the schools, their actions should be aligned with values expressed within the organization. Organizational flexibility and responsiveness, indicated by adaptability ($r = .397, p < 0.01$), have a moderate positive correlation, meaning there is a significant but less positive relationship between flexibility and satisfaction compared to involvement and consistency.

The regression analysis further confirms these findings by revealing that mission, involvement, and consistency are the areas that positively influence teacher job satisfaction. Evaluation of the coefficients of the independent variables indicates that all are significant. Therefore, it has been established that mission, involvement, and consistency affect teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon. When the schools have a precise

aim and a shared vision, participative activities, and values, they experience higher satisfaction. Consequently, the factor teachers see as relatively less important in terms of direct influence, yet highly appreciated, is adaptability. These outcomes underscore the necessity of establishing a mission-oriented, engaged, and value-atheistic organizational climate to improve teacher satisfaction meaningfully.

5.2 Suggestions and Recommendations

From the research findings of this study, the following recommendations could be made to improve teacher job satisfaction in private Christian Bible schools in North Yangon by considering organizational culture traits. These recommendations align with the study objectives: to establish the key characteristics of organizational culture that affect teacher job satisfaction, to explore the nature of the relationship between organizational culture and teacher job satisfaction, and to determine how such characteristics affect satisfaction levels.

The research also revealed that mission, involvement, and consistency significantly correlate with teacher job satisfaction. Based on this, it is suggested that these schools focus on enhancing a compelling mission statement as it ranked the highest mean value in the descriptive analysis and has implications on job satisfaction. School leaders should always communicate sustainable messages about the organizational goals and how these contribute to the teachers' purpose and vision. The mission must be communicated frequently and supported by tangible progress toward its achievement, which is expected to keep the motivation levels high among teachers.

The findings of this study revealed that involvement was the most significant predictor of teacher job satisfaction using both correlational and regression analyses. Teachers should be engaged in decision-making, and many schools should promote teamwork. Teachers should also be able to participate in organizational planning and an implementation process with commensurate delegations of power. Hence, this participatory approach will establish that teachers are valuable in their roles, increasing the rate of job satisfaction among the teachers. However, schools should pay essential attention to the issue of constancy in maintaining a reliable set of norms and ethical standards, implementing measures that encourage leadership to emulate the spoken values, and ensuring accountability for such values will cultivate trust and unity within the organization. These values should be clearly defined at all levels, along with explicit cultural norms and expectations, to retain general parameters of ethicality. Schools should also maintain direct communication with the stakeholders, learners, and feedback and embrace changes. Although it may not have such an apparent effect on satisfaction, the capability to adapt guarantees the organization focuses on alteration, which will improve the work environment's dynamics and support.

Therefore, it is suggested that private Christian Bible schools in north Yangon need to enhance mission clarification, promote teacher engagement, and practice operational consistency. Following them will significantly improve teachers' job satisfaction, making them a much more productive and dedicated workforce. Furthermore,

promoting an adaptability culture would support these efforts by maintaining responsiveness and innovation. This way, schools can achieve long-term improvement, organizational success, and teacher satisfaction.

5.3 Needs for Further Research

Based on the findings, other dimensions of the organizational culture influence teacher job satisfaction apart from the ones discussed in this study. Future researchers may have to incorporate more variables in their work and investigate more schools apart from those in North Yangon. Generalizing the research across all states and divisions in Myanmar would offer a more accurate and broader picture of how organizational culture impacts teacher job satisfaction. The researchers could increase the sample size and include various groups of people to increase external validity. Future researchers will be able to design increasingly effective strategies and participate in shaping the best working conditions in Christian Bible schools in Myanmar.

6. References

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